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Dynamics of Population Size, Density and Growth of Haryana, India (2001-2011)

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Abstract

The population of Haryana has been increasing unbaredly since four decades. The present paper attempts to analyze the trends in Population Size, Density and its Growth in the Study area during the study period. The study based on secondary data. It discusses the changing scenario of population size, density and growth during the two census year(2001-2011). The study reveals that the population has been increase in continuously and unevenly from 1960 to 2011. The distribution of population present an inverse correlation between area and population during the study period, because geographically small district are supporting more population and vice-versa. The overall growth of population has registered 19.90% increase between 2011-2011.

Key-Words: Population, Density and Growth.

Introduction

Population studies have long been the subject of concern for social scientists including demographers and geographers. Although traditionally, geography has been a matter of Academic dispute (Clarke, 1965:1) among the geographers themselves (Chandna, 2005:1). The analysis of immense significance for population geographers. Demographic characteristics act as key source to understand the demographic character of an area. Haryana state is now home to 2,53,53,081 persons as per the provisions Home Ministry of India. It constitutes about 2.09% of the total population of the country. Hence, Haryana state is one of the mid populous state of India. An overwhelming proportion of the state;s population constituting about more than 65% lives in rural areas. This indicates a massive dependence on agriculture and other relate activities.

Study area

Haryana State has come in to existence as an independent state on 1st November 1966, after the reorganization of composite state of Punjab on ling uistic. It is located in north western part of India. It stretches from 27°38' N to 30°5" north latitudes and from 74°27'8" east to 77°36'5" east longitudes. Geographically the boundaries of Haryana state found in river Ghaggar in the south west. Siwalik hills in the north east. Aravali hills are in the south and the Thar desert in south-west.

Objectives of the study

1. To examine the trends in size, growth and density of population in Haryana.
2. To analyze the spatial variation in population size growth and density of population in the study area.

Data base

The present study is based on secondary data. The data relating to population size and growth for two census years i.e 2001 and 2011 have been collected from Directorate of Census operations, Haryana and Statistical Abstract for Haryana(2013-14).

Result and Discussion

Density of Population: The density of population expressed as number of persons per unit area help in understanding the spatial distribution of population in relation to land.

Figure-1

This figure reveals that overall population density in the study area has witnessed a gradual increase from 372 persons per Sq. km in 1991 to 478 persons per Sq km in 2001. During the 2011 Census, the population density has also been increased to 573 from 478 persons per Sq. km over the period.

The study reveals that with every successive Census, the growth of population results in overcrowds. It is due to the fact that although population increase continuously, area can not expanded. The dependence on agriculture continues to be high.

Increase in Population since 2001 by Districts

Districts	Population 2011	Population 2001	Variation in Population	Growth of Population in%	Density of population (Per Sq. km)
Ambala	1136784	1014411	122373	12.06	722
Panckula	558890	468411	90479	19.32	622
Yamunagar	1214162	1041630	172352	16.56	687
Kurukshetra	964231	825454	138777	16.81	630
Kaithal	1072861	946131	12730	13.39	463
Karnal	1506323	1274183	232140	18.22	598
Panipat	1202811	964449	235362	24.33	949
Sonipat	1480080	1279175	200905	15.71	697
Rohtak	1058683	940128	118555	12.61	607
Jhajjar	956907	880072	76835	8.73	522
Faridabd	1798954	1365465	433489	31.75	2298
Palwal	1040493	821921	211372	25.49	761
Gurgaon	1514085	870539	646546	73.93	1241
Mewat	1089406	789750	299656	37.94	729
Rewari	896129	765351	130778	17.09	562
Mahandrgrah	921860	812521	109159	13.43	485
Bhiwani	1629109	1425022	204087	14.32	341
Jind	1342042	1189827	142215	11.15	493
Hisar	1742515	1537117	205698	13.38	438
Fathebad	941522	806158	135364	16.79	371
Sirsa	1295114	1116649	178465	15.98	303
Total	25353081	21144564	4208517	19.90	478

Source-Director of Census operation, Haryana

This Table indicates remarkable spatial variation in population density in 2001 in the study area. The population density varies from lowest 303 persons per Sq. km in Sirsa district to highest 2298 persons per Sq. km in Faridabad district. The district namely Gurgaon, Faridabad bordering Delhi NCR were densely populated which supported more than 1500 persons per Sq. km. The district namely Panipat is a industrial place having 949 persons per Sq. km. The population density was very low i.e less than 400 persons per Sq. km in remaining three district namely Sirsa, Jind and Fathehabad. The influence of natural and environment factors such as relief structure, climate, water supply, soil fertility and agriculture productivity is quite clear on the variations in density of population in Haryana.

**Trends in population Growth:
Districts-wise Population Growth in 2011**

Figure-2 reveals that total population of the study Area increased from 211.45 lakh to 253.53 lakh in 2011 at the growth rate 19.90%. The highest growth rate of population(73.93%) has been observed in Gurgaon district followed by Mewat(37.94%) district. Three other district namely Faridabad(31.75%), Palwal(25.49%), Panipat(24.33%) also registered high growth rate than study Area Average(19.90%). The study bring out that five district namely Grugaon, Mewat, Faridabad, Palwal and Panipat experienced a higher growth rate than study area average over the period 2001-2011. The highest growth rate(73.94%) has been observed in Gurgaon district. Remaining sixteen districts have registered growth rate less than study area average. The influence of natural and environment factors such as relief structure, climate, water supply, soil fertility and agriculture productivity is quite clear on the variations in density of population in Haryana.

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